

New Approach of Critical Theories of Eclecticism Theatre

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Abstract— Due to the fact that there was great attention to traditional taxonomies between 1981 and 2001 in Iran, many playwrights made every attempt to create an eclectic form by combining one or some elements in each form of theatre. The quality and quantity of this trend is an important issue in history and criticism of contemporary art of theatre. Having sufficient familiarity with the trend of eclecticism in Iranian art of theatre contributes to knowing contemporary art of theatre in Iran. In fact, this familiarity would be impossible or insufficient without knowing about the trend of eclecticism in Iran. The followings are some approaches for research: Gathering professors and requisite research documents, having access to analyzed and edited research documents, using research results and having certain outline for further investigation and reasoning. The researcher had collected and surveyed some of the important and published eclectic plays. Moreover, the researcher has studied the fact that how the traditional theatre and western theatre have combined together. The researcher has focused on the selections in eclectic theatres.

Keywords— Eclecticism Theatre, Traditional Taxonomies, Iran.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE present article which is written about “New approach of Critical Theories of Eclecticism Theatre in Iran” contains a new section on Theatre Studies, especially the dramatic literature. However, it is noteworthy that the current study is the starting point in this field trying to be of use in spreading knowledge and intelligence about Eclectic Theatre. Therefore, conducting research on the Iranian eclectic theatre can be considered as a recent phenomenon as being involved with Iranian theatre is a current issue. After 1978 in Iran and especially when the universities were reopened, number of dramatic art students has been increases, especially in higher education institutes. Students have performed different plays and staged many plays.

In addition, they established drama institutes and art galleries and increased dramatic performances. In the same line and for the quality of Iranian young population and their experience based performances, different dramatic works were written and numerous plays were performed. Now it is necessary to study and criticize these sets of plays and dramas (of which written documents are available).

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On the basis of taxonomy given by Farhad Nazerzadeh Kermani, the author has studied the contents and forms only. This means the author has combined the elements of contents and formal elements in different figures on the basis of special aesthetic theory and studied them in whole. The historical basis of present research is limited to the period between 1981 and 2001. It is noteworthy that limited researches have been done on this subject. The research objectives to investigate the Iranian contemporary theatre based on the said nine forms. Also, the relationships between modern dramatic works, forms, ceremonies and rites in Iranian Theatre based on a cohesive work. The role of fundamental conventions of ceremonies in elements of drama. Moreover, the present research aims to make universal the Iranian Theatre through study of eclectic theatrical forms in Iranian Theatre and using terminology of the World Theatre. The research is evaluated based on eclecticism theoretical form in the first phase and then some classifications and criteria are gained by reading these kinds of dramatic texts. For example, we can refer to "Kaboudan va Esfandyar" theatre which is an "eclectic" work in the first phase and notwithstanding its specific resource "Shahnameh (Epic poetry and legendary history of Iran by Firdausi)", after it is read, it is found that it has been created by piercing in imagination of mythical personalities; therefore, it is a valuable sample for New Approach of *Critical Theories of Eclecticism Theatre in Iran*.

II. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

The methodology is quality, based on description and analysis parameters. The data collection is in literature review. Additional searches of the theatrical literature included searches of relevant databases and University libraries for research theses on nine forms throughout of theatrical forms in Iran.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Iranian theatrical forms have been considered in nine forms based on “formal elements” and “elements of content” with a glance to standards of theatrical forms of the world. Seven forms are based on traditional origins and the other two forms are modern. 1- Ritual performances, 2-processional performances, quasitheatrical processions, 3-dramatic storytelling, performatory storytelling, theatrical storytelling, dramatic musical story telling narrative dances and narrative dances, 4- street outdoor performances and performances, 5-

puppet show, shadow play, punch and Judy show, 6- traditional farcical, 7- passion play, 8- western influenced theatre, 9- eclectic theatre.

The above mentioned seven forms have route on traditional and local field of Iran and the other two forms are influenced by western theatre and are not based on Iranian theatre and have modern origin. The said nine forms have been gained by reviewing universal knowledge in addition to theatrical developments and activities of Iran. As mentioned, traditional "ceremonies" and "rites" of Iran involve particular specifications, such as passion play, which is a traditional-Iranian rite and its fundamental conventions have not changed during the time. The ceremonies have some specifications in their structure which are evident for all people and when are placed in structure of a dramatic work, only dramatic elements are changed and the content remains unchanged. For example, the passion play of Imam Hossein Martyrdom in one dramatic structure involves the same content of the relevant ceremony and in case of any change in its dramatic element; the content shall have no change. Namira play is one of the works used the copy of Imam Hossein Martyrdom Passion Play. Namira play is one of the works used the copy of Imam Hossein Martyrdom Passion Play (mentioned in *Taziyeh: Ritual and Dram in Iran [1]* by P.J.Chelkowski) of course with some changes in dramatic elements in its structure, but the content of play is that very same of the Passion play. Indeed, all dramatic texts which have used universal or national ceremonies are subject to this specification. For this reason, the "terminology" of world theatre must be used in addition to research on Iranian theatrical forms so that researches will be scientific and universal and been evaluated concurrently with universal terminologies.

According to the researchers conducted based on *Introduction to Playwriting [2]*, the eclectic theatre is a relatively new form in the world. It seems that this theatrical form has been developed by some directors such as: Max Reinhart in Germany, Meyer hold in Russia, Mikhail Chekhov in Russia, Yevgeny Vakhtango in Russia, Alexaner Tairov in Moscow, and Peter Brook in Britain. They emerged a new style as directors; in other word, they selected forms and combined the findings with their inner thoughts and created a new phenomenon called eclectic theatre. Evans-James Rose has pointed in *Experimental Theatre [3]*: Reinhart is an eclectic director who tries to perform theatre based on his goals and gives it a new identity. He performed his theatre in circus and even in church and by creating a relationship between the viewers and actors, he broke the limitations of these two groups like classic eras and allocated anywhere for performance. He perhaps believed that performance is not merely possible on the stage and it may be performed at anyplace.

Reinhart brought King Oedipus Drama on the stage at Circus Schumann in 1980 in Frankfort and tried to maintain the continuity of viewer and actor again which traced back to Greece classic theatre. He hoped that this theatre can attract modern life similar to the large square containing Greece

society. Eclectics achieved eclecticism first through elements of forms and various styles and then combined the eclectics based on their aims and objects and give it a new identity. Vakhtango is one of the directors which is recognized as eclectic director. He combined the viewpoints and attitudes of Meyer hold and Stanislavski's realism and emerged a theatrical form known as eclectic theatre. The Vakhtango's performances are unique due to the eclectic style of psychological reality with an eminent knowledge of dramatic aspects and to Vakhtango, realism does not interpret everything from the life, but it only takes the objects required for stage restoration. Form must be created by fantasy, for this reason I call it fantastic realism, the working devices should be dramatic. He also says: Forget artificial imitation from the life; theatre has its own reality and realism.

Oscar Bracket says in *History of World's Theatre [4]*: "Tairov is an eclectic director. He named his works as eclectic theatre and believed that "Theatre is solely an art aiming to train skilled actors who would be able to improvise a though in form of dell'Arte Commedia and perform it in front of viewers. He believed in something that he himself named it eclectic theatre which encourages a group of people with talents of ballet, opera, circus, music and drama. He generally believed that "There is no relationship between art and life and theatre should be considered something similar to holy dances in ancient worship places. Therefore, the eclectic theatre term, the title allocated to his works by himself, means eclectic nature of traditional forms (such as holy dances) with contemporary theatrical forms. Based on *There is no secret [5]*, Peter Brook selected Mantegh o Teir, the masterpiece of the twelfth century (6th A.H.) written by Farideddin Atar that would be understandable for all people if it is performed at anyplace. In fact, Brook has tried to emerge eclectic theatre which was created based on mystical elements of an Iranian Poet.

Eclecticism is a new style in Iran like other areas of the world. Among its distinguished samples we can refer to Mirzadeh Eshghi, Gholamali Fekri, Aliasghar Garmsiri and Noushin. Yahya Aryanpur has pointed in *Saba ta Nima [6]*: Mirzadeh Eshghi (1893-1924) combined the western opera with Iranian theatre and formed a new style of opera which is classified in eclectic theatre based on theatrical forms, such as "Rastakhiz Salatin Iran Opera (Iranian Kings Resurrection Opeara)". "Rastakhiz Salatin Iran Opera" which is also known as "Rastakhiz Shahriaran Iran" is a fantastic, poetic and musical picture of the splendour eras of Ancient Iran and its only real personality is the author (Mirzadeh Eshghi) which is manifested with the dress of traveller man. What recognizes this work as an eclectic theatre is using national anthems and one melody of Leily & Majnoun Opera, parts of which have been narrated; in fact its music is based on Iranian forms. Moreover, narration, which is another symbol of Iranian forms, is seen in this work. Mirzadeh Eshghi has taken the advantages of dramatic elements of the western opera based on theatrical forms of Iran in creation of this work; therefore, the drama or opera of "Rastakhir" is considered as an eclectic

work and Mirzadeh Eshghi is an eclecticist.

Mostafa Oskouei said in *History of Iranian's Theatre* [7]: The Ferdowsi's Millennium was held in 1935 by innovators of these ceremonies, i.e. Mohammad Ali Foroughi and Mojtaba Minavi. Noushin, Fekri and Garmshir were invited to this memorial so that they select three stories of "Shahname Firdausi (the epic and legendary history of Iran by Firdausi)" and perform them. They selected some dramas named Rostam va Sohrab, Zal and Roudabeh (lyric), Ghobad (epic) and Rostam and Tahmineh (mythical) and brought them on the stage. These eclectic theatres were performed in Ferdowsi's Memorial in 1935.

Plays studied in this research were criticized in two formats. First the plays which have been criticized in Eclecticism based on six forms of plays that are included: Theme, Message, style, genre, conventional theatre;

In Critical Theories of Eclecticism Theatre in Iran, we continuously deal with special terminologies and indicators, theatrical styles and forms, plot expression) which has briefly been manifested) theme and theatre convention due to investigation and criticize of the eclectic plays. In fact, theatres are investigated based on these specifications. Some eclectic theatres are as follows: *Closet (Pastoukhaneh)*[8] written by Hamid Amjad, *Kalat Document of Victory (Fathname ye Kalat)*[9], *Pardehkhane* [10], *Slaves' Document of War (Jangname ye Gholaman)*[11] written by Bahram Beizaei, *All Sons of Kaveh (Hame ye Pesaran Kaveh)*[12], written by Alaeddin Rahimi, *Knapsack (Koulebar)*[13], written by Farhad Nazerzadeh Kermani, *Namira* [14] written by Nematollah Larian, *Siavosh's Grief (Souge Siavash)* [15] written by Sadegh Hatefi, *Kaboudan va Esfandyar* [16] written by Arman Omid. According to *Eclecticism theatre in Iran* [17] by Farideh Alizadeh, the play of *Fathname ye Kalat*, *Koulebar*, *Hame ye Pesaran Kaveh*, *Kaboudan va Esfandyar* of theatrical storytelling and western theatre are obtained. *Pardehkhaneh*, *Pastoukhaneh* and *Jangname ye Gholaman* are obtained of farcical play and western play. *Souge Siavash* and *Namira* are got passion play and western theatre. Among the plays mentioned, six of them are made based on tragedy and two of them are throughout farcical and one has been written based on tragicomedy. Six plays in field of symbolism and four ones are written based on realism. It is important to note that number of the plays are included by tragedy, both modern and classical tragedy, such as *Hame ye Pesaran Kaveh*, *Souge Siavash* based on legendary and in *Koulebar* based on socio- economic. The present research has been done on one of the theatrical forms and what is considered basic and fundamental.

IV. CONCLUSION

The present research has been done on one of the theatrical forms and what is considered basic and fundamental. There are other areas around the theatre forms that should research and new findings obtained. There are other areas around the theatre forms that should research and new findings obtained.

The present research is based on masterpieces, excellent

dramas and medium dramas. The research is evaluated based on eclecticism theoretical form in the first phase and then some classifications and criteria are gained by reading these kinds of dramatic texts.

The theatres, which have been used by the researcher, have been published for the first time in between 1981 and 2001, although some of them have been written in previous years.

This research does not deal with radio and television theatres and also children and young adults dramas and only the theatres will be selected which have been published in form of a book.

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